

CFD Analysis of the Hydrogen Tank Filling Process

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Abstract— In this study, the filling process of a high-pressure hydrogen tank is investigated using a transient Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) approach. The continuity, momentum, and energy equations are solved simultaneously, and the Redlich–Kwong real gas equation of state is employed to accurately represent the thermodynamic behaviour of hydrogen under high-pressure conditions. The tank is modelled as a two-dimensional axisymmetric domain under the assumption of axial symmetry, and the computational domain includes both the inlet nozzle and the internal volume of the tank. The results demonstrate the transient evolution of the pressure, temperature, and velocity fields inside the tank during the filling process. The pressure field exhibits a continuously increasing trend and gradually becomes more uniform, while the temperature field rises and spreads throughout the tank volume. The velocity field is dominated by a high-momentum jet at the inlet during the early stages of filling, and as the process progresses, the velocity levels decrease and the flow transitions toward a more quiescent regime. The findings indicate that the hydrogen filling process is a complex and strongly time-dependent problem that requires the coupled evaluation of flow dynamics and thermodynamic behaviour. This study shows that a CFD-based approach incorporating real gas effects provides a physically consistent and reliable framework for analysing the filling processes of high-pressure hydrogen storage tanks.

Keywords: Hydrogen Tank, High-Pressure Storage, Hydrogen Filling Process, CFD, Real Gas Redlich–Kwong

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing global demand for clean and sustainable energy systems, hydrogen has emerged as a promising energy carrier due to its high energy density and environmentally friendly characteristics. When used in fuel cells, hydrogen produces only water as a by-product, making it an attractive alternative to conventional fossil fuels, particularly in transportation and energy storage applications. Therefore, the development of safe and efficient hydrogen storage systems has become a critical requirement for the widespread adoption of hydrogen-based technologies [1].

Among hydrogen storage methods, high-pressure hydrogen tanks are widely preferred due to their technological maturity. However, the filling process involves coupled phenomena, including pressure increase, temperature rise due to gas compression, transient flow behaviour, and real gas effects. These factors affect the safety, performance, and durability of hydrogen storage systems. Therefore, understanding the filling process is essential for the design and optimization of high-pressure hydrogen tanks [2].

Experimental investigations of hydrogen filling processes often involve high costs, safety risks, and measurement limitations under extreme pressure conditions. In this context, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is a powerful tool for analysing hydrogen storage systems. CFD enables detailed investigation of the temporal and spatial evolution of pressure, temperature, and velocity fields within the tank, providing insights difficult to obtain experimentally [3].

A considerable number of studies in the literature have focused on both experimental and numerical analysis of hydrogen tank filling processes. Heitsch et al. experimentally investigated the thermal effects during fast hydrogen filling and demonstrated that temperature rise is a critical parameter for system safety [4]. Melideo et al. conducted CFD simulations of hydrogen tank filling and emptying processes, highlighting the transient evolution of pressure, temperature, and velocity fields [5]. Bourgeois et al. numerically analysed the influence of tank geometry and inlet conditions on temperature distribution and showed that these parameters significantly affect thermal stratification and peak temperature levels [6].

More recent studies have emphasized the importance of real gas effects in accurately predicting hydrogen filling behaviour under high-pressure conditions. Zhao et al. investigated the fast-filling process using both experimental and numerical approaches and highlighted the limitations of ideal gas assumptions [7]. Monteiro et al. performed CFD simulations using different equations of state and demonstrated that real gas models, such as Redlich–Kwong and Peng–Robinson, provide significantly improved accuracy in predicting thermodynamic properties compared to ideal gas models [8].

Despite these advancements, many studies rely on experimental observations or simplified models that do not fully capture the coupled transient and thermodynamic nature of hydrogen filling. This study analyses a high-pressure hydrogen tank filling process using a transient CFD approach, solving the governing equations of mass, momentum, and energy with the Redlich–Kwong real gas model. The tank is modelled as a two-dimensional axisymmetric domain for computational efficiency while preserving essential physics. The results provide insight into flow and thermodynamic behaviour, supporting the design and safety assessment of high-pressure hydrogen storage systems.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Model Description

The hydrogen tank filling process was investigated using a transient Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) framework to accurately capture the coupled interaction between flow dynamics and thermodynamic effects. The numerical model was constructed based on the physical configuration of a high-pressure hydrogen storage system, including both the inlet nozzle and the internal tank volume. The adopted modelling approach enables the analysis of time-dependent variations in pressure, temperature, and velocity fields throughout the filling process. Particular attention was given to the selection of appropriate assumptions, boundary conditions, and thermodynamic models in order to ensure a physically consistent and reliable representation of high-pressure hydrogen behaviour.

Figure 1 presents the real physical configuration of the high-pressure hydrogen storage tank modelled in this study. This image illustrates the geometric features and overall structure of the system that form the basis of the numerical model. The cylindrical shape of the tank, the inlet nozzle connection, and the flow development along the axial direction support the suitability of the two-dimensional axisymmetric approach adopted in the CFD model. This consistency between the real system and the numerical model strengthens the validity of the assumptions and enhances the engineering interpretability of the obtained results.

Fig. 1 Hydrogen Tank

Figure 2 presents the geometric model of the hydrogen tank employed in the CFD analysis. The model was constructed by simplifying the real system into a two-dimensional axisymmetric domain, which enables a significant reduction in computational cost while retaining the dominant physical characteristics of the filling process. The computational domain encompasses both the inlet nozzle and the internal tank volume, allowing accurate representation of the inflow conditions and the development of the flow field within the tank. This geometric representation provides a reliable and efficient basis for capturing the transient behaviour of pressure, temperature, and velocity fields during the hydrogen filling process.

Fig. 2 The Geometric Model

Figure 3 presents the numerical model used in the CFD analysis of the hydrogen tank filling process. The computational domain was defined to include both the internal volume of the tank and the inlet nozzle region, and the hydrogen filling was modelled using a mass flow rate boundary condition. A constant mass flow rate of 8 g/s was specified at the inlet, while the initial conditions inside the tank were defined as 20 bar pressure and 25°C temperature. Appropriate thermal boundary conditions were applied to the tank walls, and the energy equation was activated to accurately capture the temperature variations resulting from gas compression. The solution was carried out in a transient manner, and at each time step, the continuity, momentum, and energy equations were solved simultaneously. In order to accurately represent the real gas behaviour of hydrogen under high-pressure conditions, the Redlich–Kwong equation of state was employed. All simulations were performed using ANSYS Fluent, and the visualization results were obtained from the sectional plane shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 The Numerical Model

B. Governing Equations

Conservation of Mass:

The principle of conservation of mass states that the difference between the mass entering and leaving a control volume is equal to the rate of change of mass within that control volume. This principle constitutes one of the fundamental laws of fluid mechanics and forms the basis of all physical and numerical models used to describe fluid flow. Mass can neither be created nor destroyed within a flow field; it can only be transported in space and time. The mathematical expression of this principle is given by the continuity equation, which in its general form is written as [9]:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho v) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where:

- ρ denotes the fluid density (kg/m³),
- v represents the velocity vector (m/s),
- t is the time (s).

This equation states that the temporal variation of density within a control volume is balanced by the net mass flux due to fluid motion across its boundaries. The first term accounts for the local (time-dependent) change in density, while the second term represents the convective transport of mass through the flow field. Together, these terms ensure that mass is conserved both locally and globally [9].

The continuity equation is solved simultaneously with the momentum and energy conservation equations to determine the flow field variables in a physically consistent manner. Its accurate satisfaction is a prerequisite for the reliability of the computed velocity, pressure, and density fields. Therefore, the continuity equation occupies a central position in the theoretical formulation of fluid flow problems and constitutes an essential component of all CFD-based modelling approaches [9].

Conservation of Momentum:

The principle of conservation of momentum is based on Newton's second law and states that the rate of change of momentum of a fluid element is equal to the sum of the forces acting on it. In fluid flow, these forces arise mainly from pressure gradients and viscous stresses. The momentum equation provides the fundamental relationship that governs the motion of the fluid and describes how the velocity field evolves in space and time. In its general vector form, the momentum conservation equation is written as [10]:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho v v) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \tau \quad (2)$$

where:

- p denotes the pressure (Pa),
- τ represents the viscous stress tensor (Pa),
- $\rho v v$ represents the convective flux of momentum (N/m³).

This equation represents the balance between inertial effects, pressure forces, and viscous forces within the flow

field. The left-hand side accounts for the temporal and convective transport of momentum, while the right-hand side includes the forces acting on the fluid element [10].

For a Newtonian fluid, the viscous stress tensor τ is expressed as [10]:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot v) \delta_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where:

- μ is the dynamic viscosity (Pa·s),
- δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta.

This formulation relates the viscous stresses to the velocity gradients and ensures that the effects of internal friction within the fluid are properly accounted for in the momentum balance [10].

The momentum equation is solved simultaneously with the continuity and energy equations to obtain a complete description of the flow field. It determines the velocity and pressure distributions and plays a central role in predicting the dynamic behaviour of the fluid. The accurate representation of momentum transport is essential for ensuring the physical consistency and reliability of the numerical solution [10].

Conservation of Energy:

The principle of conservation of energy describes how the total energy within a system varies with time and constitutes the fundamental basis of the thermal and mechanical interactions in a flow field. Since the temperature distribution in a fluid is directly related to the pressure and velocity fields, the energy equation represents one of the most important governing equations for describing the thermodynamic behaviour of the flow. For a compressible flow, the energy equation is expressed in the following general form [11]:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho E)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (v(\rho E + p)) = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + \Phi \quad (4)$$

where:

- E denotes the total energy per unit mass (J/kg),
- k denotes the thermal conductivity (W/m·K),
- T denotes the temperature (K),
- Φ represents the viscous dissipation term (W/m³).

This equation accounts simultaneously for the temporal variation of the total energy, the convective transport of energy due to fluid motion, the heat transfer by thermal conduction, and the conversion of mechanical energy into thermal energy caused by viscous effects. The terms on the left-hand side represent the time-dependent change and convective transport of energy, whereas the terms on the right-hand side correspond to heat conduction and viscous dissipation, respectively [11].

The total energy per unit mass is defined as the sum of the internal energy, the flow work, and the kinetic energy, and is given by [11]:

$$E = h - \frac{p}{\rho} + \frac{|v|^2}{2} \quad (5)$$

This formulation enables the energy balance in the flow field to be evaluated by simultaneously considering both thermal and mechanical contributions. The energy equation makes it possible to account for the temperature rise caused by gas compression, the kinetic energy associated with fluid motion, and the heat transfer occurring through conduction and convection mechanisms. Therefore, it plays a central role in the accurate and physically consistent prediction of the temperature field and heat distribution within the system [11].

First Law of Thermodynamics and Energy Balance:

The first law of thermodynamics is based on the principle of conservation of energy and states that the change in the total energy of a system is determined by the energy exchange between the system and its surroundings. This law provides the fundamental framework for describing any physical process from an energy perspective. When a control volume approach is adopted, the energy balance is formulated in terms of the energy transported by mass flow and the heat transfer between the system and the environment. The general form of the energy balance can be written as [12]:

$$\frac{dU}{dt} = \dot{m}_{in}h_{in} + \dot{Q} \quad (6)$$

where:

- U denotes the total internal energy stored within the control volume [J],
- \dot{m}_{in} represents the mass flow rate entering the control volume [kg/s],
- h_{in} is the specific enthalpy of the incoming flow [J/kg],
- \dot{Q} denotes the rate of heat transfer between the system and its surroundings [W].

This expression indicates that the time rate of change of the internal energy within a system is governed by the energy carried by the incoming mass flow and by the heat exchanged with the environment. The energy balance provides a macroscopic description of the thermodynamic behaviour of the system and clarifies the mechanisms through which energy is transported and transformed during a given process [12].

This integral form of the energy balance constitutes the thermodynamic foundation of the differential energy equation used in Computational Fluid Dynamics. In CFD, the energy equation represents the localized and time-dependent form of this balance, applied at every point of the flow domain. In other words, the numerical solution of the energy equation ensures that the first law of thermodynamics is satisfied locally and instantaneously throughout the computational domain [12].

Therefore, the first law of thermodynamics, together with the energy balance formulation, plays a central role in establishing a physically consistent description of the thermal behaviour of the system. It provides the theoretical basis for predicting temperature fields, energy transport, and heat distribution in fluid flow problems [12].

Real Gas Redlich–Kwong:

The Redlich–Kwong real gas equation of state is a semi-empirical thermodynamic model developed to account for the deviations of real gases from ideal gas behaviour, particularly under moderate and high-pressure conditions. It provides a more realistic relationship between pressure, temperature, and density by incorporating the effects of intermolecular interactions and the finite volume occupied by gas molecules. Owing to its simplicity and reasonable accuracy over a wide range of operating conditions, the Redlich–Kwong model has been widely used in engineering and thermodynamic applications. The Redlich–Kwong equation of state is expressed as [13]:

$$p = \frac{RT}{v-b} - \frac{a}{\sqrt{T}v(v+b)} \quad (7)$$

where:

- p is the pressure [Pa],
- T is the temperature [K],
- v is the specific volume [m^3/kg],
- R is the specific gas constant of the fluid [$J/(kg \cdot K)$],
- a and b are substance-specific constants determined experimentally.

In this formulation, the first term represents the ideal gas contribution, while the second term introduces a correction that accounts for intermolecular attractive forces and real gas effects. As a result, the Redlich–Kwong equation provides a more physically accurate description of gas behaviour compared to the ideal gas law [13].

The relationship between the specific volume and the density is given by [13]:

$$v = \frac{1}{\rho} \quad (8)$$

which allows the equation of state to be expressed in terms of pressure, temperature, and density [13].

Real gas behaviour is commonly characterized using the compressibility factor Z , defined as [13]:

$$Z = \frac{p}{\rho RT} \quad (9)$$

For an ideal gas, $Z=1$, whereas for real gases Z deviates from unity depending on the pressure and temperature. At elevated pressure levels, this deviation becomes significant and the ideal gas assumption may lead to considerable inaccuracies in the prediction of thermodynamic properties. The Redlich–Kwong equation of state implicitly accounts for these deviations by incorporating real gas corrections, thereby improving the accuracy of density, enthalpy, and internal energy predictions [13].

Therefore, the Redlich–Kwong real gas model provides a reliable and practical framework for representing the thermodynamic behaviour of gases in regimes where ideal gas assumptions are no longer valid, and it is particularly well suited for applications involving high-pressure gas systems [13].

III.RESULTS

In this section, the numerical results of the hydrogen tank filling process are presented, and the time-dependent evolution of pressure, temperature, and velocity fields is analysed in detail. The results indicate that the filling process is strongly transient in nature and that flow dynamics and thermodynamic effects are closely coupled. In particular, the variations in pressure, temperature, and velocity fields are evaluated together to provide a comprehensive understanding of the system behaviour.

Figure 4 shows the time-dependent variation of pressure inside the tank. The results indicate that the pressure increases continuously and monotonically throughout the filling process. Starting from an initial value of approximately 20 bar, the pressure reaches nearly 350 bar at the end of the process. A good agreement between the numerical results and experimental data is observed, which supports the accuracy of the developed model. As the filling progresses, the rate of pressure increase slightly changes, indicating a transition toward a more stable regime.

Fig. 4 Comparison of Pressure Evolution Inside the Hydrogen Tank

Figure 5 presents the time-dependent variation of temperature inside the tank. The results show a rapid temperature increase during the initial stage of the filling process. This behaviour is mainly attributed to gas compression under high-pressure conditions. As the process continues, the rate of temperature increase decreases, and the system exhibits a more stable thermal behaviour. A reasonable agreement between the numerical and experimental results is observed, indicating that the model successfully captures the thermodynamic behaviour of hydrogen.

Fig. 5 Comparison of Temperature Evolution Inside the Hydrogen Tank

Figure 6 illustrates the pressure distribution inside the tank at three different time steps. At the initial stage (1), the pressure levels are relatively low, and localized effects near the inlet region are dominant. At the intermediate stage (2), the pressure increases and spreads over a larger portion of the tank volume. At the final stage (3), the pressure distribution becomes nearly uniform throughout the tank, indicating that the system approaches equilibrium conditions as the filling process progresses.

Fig. 6 Time-Dependent Pressure Distribution Inside the Hydrogen Tank

Figure 7 shows the temperature distribution inside the tank at three different time steps. At the initial stage (1), the temperature remains relatively low, with slight increases near the inlet region. At the intermediate stage (2), the temperature rises significantly due to compression effects and begins to spread throughout the tank. At the final stage (3), the temperature distribution becomes more uniform, reaching its maximum levels across the tank volume. These results clearly demonstrate the impact of gas compression and energy transport mechanisms during the filling process.

Fig. 7 Time-Dependent Temperature Distribution Inside the Hydrogen Tank

Figure 8 presents the velocity distribution inside the tank at three different time steps. At the initial stage (1), a high-momentum jet is formed at the inlet, leading to maximum velocity levels. At the intermediate stage (2), as the internal tank pressure increases, the driving force at the inlet decreases, resulting in a reduction in velocity levels. At the final stage (3), the flow becomes significantly damped, and the system transitions toward a low-velocity, quasi-stagnant regime. This behaviour indicates that the system evolves from a flow-dominated regime at the beginning to a thermodynamically controlled regime in the later stages of the filling process.

Fig. 8 Time-Dependent Velocity Distribution Inside the Hydrogen Tank

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the hydrogen tank filling process was investigated using a transient Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) approach, incorporating the Redlich–Kwong real gas equation of state to accurately represent hydrogen behaviour under high-pressure conditions. The developed numerical model successfully captured the coupled evolution of pressure, temperature, and velocity fields during the filling process, providing a comprehensive understanding of the underlying physical mechanisms.

The results showed that the pressure inside the tank increases continuously and reaches approximately 350 bar at the end of the filling process, while the pressure distribution gradually becomes more uniform throughout the tank volume. Similarly, the temperature rises significantly due to gas compression, reaching values close to 100°C, and evolves toward a more homogeneous distribution over time. These findings are consistent with the expected behaviour of compressible gases and highlight the importance of considering real gas effects for accurate thermodynamic predictions.

The velocity field is initially dominated by a high-momentum jet at the inlet, resulting in strong local gradients. However, as the internal pressure increases, the driving force decreases, leading to a gradual reduction in velocity levels. In the final stage, the flow transitions into a low-velocity, quasi-stagnant regime, indicating a shift from a flow-dominated to a thermodynamically controlled process during filling.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the hydrogen filling process is strongly transient and governed by the coupled interaction between flow dynamics and thermodynamic effects. The use of a real gas model plays a crucial role in accurately predicting pressure and temperature evolution under high-pressure conditions. The proposed CFD approach provides a reliable and physically consistent framework for analysing hydrogen tank filling processes and offers valuable insights for the design, optimization, and safety assessment of high-pressure hydrogen storage systems. Furthermore, the presented methodology can serve as a reference for future studies aiming to improve the accuracy of hydrogen storage modelling under realistic operating conditions.

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